

Urban Analytic Platform: A Unified Web-Based Infrastructure for Integrated Urban Mobility Research

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1 Introduction

Urban mobility research increasingly relies on the integration of heterogeneous spatial data sources, analytical methods, and disciplinary perspectives. Questions related to accessibility, environmental exposure, travel behavior, and lived urban experiences require the combination of administrative datasets, sensor-based measurements, participatory information, and derived spatial indicators. Despite this need for integration, current research practices remain fragmented. Data are typically accessed through separate portals, processed through project-specific scripts, analyzed in isolated computational environments, and shared in ways that limit transparency, reproducibility, and transferability across studies and contexts. These challenges are particularly pronounced in multidisciplinary settings, where differing technical standards, analytical practices, and levels of geospatial expertise can further hinder collaboration.

This poster presents the Urban Analytic Platform (UAP), an ongoing research infrastructure initiative developed as part of the Geoportti Finnish National Research Infrastructure to support integrated urban mobility research through a unified, web-based analytical environment. UAP is conceived as a modular platform that connects data access, spatial analysis, and result dissemination within a coherent pipeline, supporting

exploratory analysis, reproducible workflows, and results sharing across projects and disciplinary contexts. The platform responds to a growing demand in geographic information science for infrastructures that enable not only visualization and data sharing, but also the execution and reuse of analytical workflows in a transparent and reproducible manner.

2 Methods

From a system perspective, UAP adopts a service-oriented architecture that separates user interaction, data services, and computational analysis. A web-based frontend provides interactive access to datasets, maps, and analytical tools, while a backend API coordinates data retrieval, validation, and job execution. Spatial data are managed in a spatial database and exposed through standard web services, enabling both internal platform use and external access through widely adopted GIS protocols. Rather than building all components from scratch, UAP is designed to facilitate access and to build on available national data resources and computational infrastructures, exploring how these can be unified into a coherent user-facing platform.

3 Results

Current development results focus on the system design and prototype implementation of the platform architecture. The initial prototype demonstrates a basic workflow from dataset access through standardized interfaces to map-based visualization, showing the end-to-end process from data services to user-facing exploration. The prototype provides an initial proof-of-concept for the platform architecture, with further development and evaluation planned. The current design

reflects a modular approach guiding the organization of data access, analytical tools, and visualization within the platform.

4 Conclusion

The scientific contribution of UAP lies in its role as an enabling infrastructure for integrated urban mobility analysis. First, the platform supports the systematic integration of mobility-related data from multiple sources, creating opportunities for data fusion across spatial and temporal scales. This includes the potential to combine relatively static spatial layers with dynamically updated mobility indicators, opening pathways toward more responsive analytical approaches. Second, by embedding analytical tools within a shared platform, UAP encourages the reuse and comparison of methods across studies, contributing to greater methodological consistency and cumulative knowledge building. Third, the platform foregrounds issues of transparency and transferability that are central to contemporary GIScience. By explicitly linking data, analytical parameters, and outputs, UAP facilitates the inspection and replication of analytical workflows, making it easier to assess how results are produced and under what assumptions. Providing a structured environment for sharing both data and analytical processes supports critical evaluation and reuse beyond individual case studies.

Importantly, UAP is presented as an evolving research platform rather than a finalized system. Its modular design allows analytical components, data sources, and interface elements to be adapted as research needs and technical possibilities develop. In this sense, this unified environment also serves as a testbed for exploring how web-based GIS architecture can support integrated, interdisciplinary urban research without constraining methodological innovation.

Data and Software Availability

This poster presents the conceptual model and system architecture of the Urban Analytic Platform; no new empirical datasets are introduced, and implementation details are provided at the level of infrastructure design rather than executable software release.

Declaration of Generative AI in writing

The authors declare that they have used Generative AI tools in the preparation of this manuscript. Specifically, the AI tools were utilized for language editing but not for generating scientific content, research data, or substantive conclusions. All intellectual and creative work, including the analysis and interpretation of data, is original and has been conducted by the authors without AI assistance.

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